

ANFIS-Based Maximum Power Transfer and Stability Enhancement in Grid Connected Solar PV using MATLAB-Simulink

B. Sekhar, R. Sindhuja, N. Naga Prasanth, V. Harsha Vardhan, M. Khaja Mohiddin

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Vasireddy Venkatadri Institute of Technology, Pedakakani, Namburu, Guntur, India.

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KEYWORDS

ANFIS,
Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT),
Grid-Connected PV,
Voltage Source Converter (VSC),
P-Q Control,
MATLAB-Simulink,
Power Stability,
Renewable Energy,
Solar Power.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS)-based control strategy for maximizing power transfer and enhancing stability in a grid-connected solar photovoltaic (PV) system. The proposed system is designed and implemented using MATLAB-Simulink to ensure efficient real-time simulation. ANFIS is employed to optimize the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) process, enabling the extraction of maximum available solar power under varying irradiation and temperature conditions. Additionally, an independent active and reactive power (P-Q) control strategy is integrated with a voltage source converter (VSC) to ensure stable and efficient power transfer to the grid. The effectiveness of the proposed controller is evaluated through detailed simulations under different environmental conditions, demonstrating its ability to maintain system stability and improve overall power quality. Simulation results validate the superiority of the proposed approach in achieving enhanced performance and reliability in grid-connected PV systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for renewable energy sources has led to the rapid growth of photovoltaic (PV) systems, particularly in grid-connected applications. Solar energy is one of the most promising renewable sources due to its abundance, sustainability, and decreasing cost of

implementation [1]. However, the intermittent nature of solar energy, caused by variations in solar irradiation and temperature, poses significant challenges in ensuring optimal energy extraction and stable grid integration [2]. These variations can lead to fluctuations in power generation, affecting grid stability and power

quality. Therefore, an efficient control strategy for grid-connected PV systems is essential to maximize power transfer and maintain stable operation under dynamic environmental conditions. Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) techniques play a crucial role in optimizing the energy harvested from PV panels. Conventional MPPT algorithms such as Perturb and Observe (P&O), Incremental Conductance (INC), and Hill Climbing methods are widely used due to their simplicity and ease of implementation [3]–[5]. However, these methods often suffer from limitations such as slow tracking speed, steady-state oscillations, and reduced efficiency under rapidly changing weather conditions [6]. To overcome these drawbacks, intelligent MPPT techniques based on artificial intelligence (AI) have gained significant attention in recent years. Among AI-based techniques, the Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) has emerged as a powerful tool for MPPT due to its ability to combine the learning capability of artificial neural networks (ANNs) with the decision-making ability of fuzzy logic control (FLC) [7]. ANFIS-based MPPT can adapt to nonlinear PV characteristics, improve tracking accuracy, and enhance response time under fluctuating solar conditions [8], [9]. Unlike conventional MPPT algorithms, ANFIS can effectively handle partial shading scenarios, reducing power losses and ensuring optimal performance [10]. Several studies have demonstrated the superiority of ANFIS-based MPPT in terms of higher efficiency, reduced oscillations, and improved dynamic performance [11]–[13]. In addition to MPPT, effective power control strategies are essential for ensuring stable integration of PV systems with the grid. A voltage source converter (VSC)-based control approach enables independent regulation of active and reactive power (P-Q control), ensuring smooth power injection into the grid while maintaining voltage stability and power factor correction [14]. Proper management of active and reactive power is crucial for avoiding grid disturbances, voltage fluctuations, and harmonic distortions in grid-connected PV systems [15]. The combination of ANFIS-based MPPT with VSC-based P-Q control can significantly improve the overall performance and stability of grid-connected PV systems. Several research studies have explored the integration of AI-based MPPT techniques with grid-connected PV systems. For instance, [16] proposed an ANFIS-based MPPT strategy

for a grid-connected PV system and demonstrated its effectiveness in improving power transfer efficiency. In [17], a comparative analysis of AI-based MPPT methods, including fuzzy logic, neural networks, and ANFIS, was conducted, highlighting ANFIS as the most effective approach for handling nonlinearities in PV systems. Similarly, [18] investigated the impact of ANFIS-based MPPT on power quality and grid stability, revealing a significant reduction in harmonic distortions and improved voltage regulation. This paper presents a detailed investigation into the implementation of ANFIS-based MPPT and P-Q control strategies for a grid-connected PV system using MATLAB-Simulink. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is evaluated under varying solar irradiation and temperature conditions. Additionally, an induction motor is connected to the DC link, where an inverter-based speed controller is used to regulate motor performance. The system configuration enables both grid integration and motor-driven applications, ensuring efficient energy utilization. Simulation results demonstrate the superiority of the proposed method in terms of maximizing power transfer, improving system stability, and enhancing grid compatibility.

2. PROPOSED SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The proposed system combines a grid-connected photovoltaic array with an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS)-based Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) controller and a Voltage Source Converter (VSC)-based P-Q power control strategy to ensure efficient energy transfer and grid stability. The PV array converts solar radiation into electrical power, which is highly dependent on environmental conditions like solar irradiation and temperature. The ANFIS-based MPPT controller adjusts the duty cycle of a Boost Converter to regulate PV voltage and maintain operation at the Maximum Power Point. The regulated DC output is supplied to a Voltage Source Converter (VSC), which performs DC-to-AC conversion for seamless grid integration. The VSC independently controls both active and reactive power, ensuring efficient power transfer and maintaining grid stability. A Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) synchronizes the inverter output with grid voltage, and an induction motor is connected for speed control. This configuration supports both grid integration and motor-driven applications, making it a

versatile solution for renewable energy-based systems. The MATLAB-Simulink environment was used for detailed simulation and validation.

3. DESIGN AND MODELING OF PROPOSED SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

A. Solar PV Generation System

The proposed grid-connected photovoltaic (PV) system consists of several key components designed to ensure maximum power extraction and efficient power transfer to the grid. The system comprises a PV array, a DC-DC boost converter with an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy

Inference System (ANFIS)-based MPPT controller, a voltage source converter (VSC), and a grid interface unit. The PV array is the primary energy source, converting solar radiation into electrical energy. The output power of the PV array is dependent on environmental factors such as solar irradiation and temperature. To ensure the PV array operates at its Maximum Power Point (MPP), an ANFIS-based MPPT controller is implemented, which dynamically adjusts the duty cycle of the boost converter to regulate the DC voltage. The boost converter steps up the PV voltage to the required DC link voltage, ensuring efficient power conversion and stable operation.

Fig.1 Proposed ANFIS controller based grid connected solar PV system

a. Solar PV Boost Converter Configuration with ANFIS Controller

A solar photovoltaic (PV) system with a boost converter is essential for efficiently extracting and regulating power before integrating it into a load or the grid. The PV system consists of a solar panel that converts sunlight into electrical energy, which varies depending on environmental conditions. To step up the voltage to the desired level, a DC-DC converter is required. The boost converter, a type of DC-DC converter, consists of an inductor, a switch, a diode, and an output capacitor. To ensure maximum power extraction from the PV system, a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm is integrated into the control system. The Perturb and Observe (P&O) MPPT algorithm is commonly used due to its simplicity and effectiveness. It works by periodically perturbing the operating voltage of the PV module and observing the corresponding change in power. However, the P&O method can exhibit

steady-state oscillations around the MPP, especially under rapidly changing irradiation conditions. To enhance the performance of the system and overcome the limitations of traditional MPPT techniques, an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) controller is employed. This controller combines the learning capability of artificial neural networks (ANNs) with the decision-making logic of fuzzy inference systems, making it an intelligent and adaptive control strategy. ANFIS can dynamically adjust the duty cycle of the boost converter based on real-time variations in solar irradiation and temperature. The regulated DC output voltage from the boost converter can be fed into an inverter for grid connection or used directly to charge batteries or power DC loads.

Fig.2 solar PV system with ANFIS controller

1. Single-Diode Solar PV Model: Designing a single-diode solar PV model involves analyzing the electrical characteristics of a photovoltaic (PV) cell. The single-diode model is one of the most commonly used to simulate the behavior of a PV cell. This model includes one diode, a current source, and series and shunt resistances to represent losses as shown in fig.3.

2. Basic Equation of the Single-Diode Model: The equation that governs the behavior of the single-diode PV model is derived from Kirchoff's current law (KCL):

$$I = I_{ph} - I_D - I_{sh} \quad (1)$$

Where: I = output current of the PV module (A), I_{ph} = photocurrent, the current generated by light (A), I_D = diode current (A), I_{sh} = shunt current (A)

Fig. 3 equivalent model of PV solar.

3. Diode Current (I_D): The current through the diode is described by the Shockley diode equation:

$$I_D = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I R_s}{n V_t}} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

Where: I_0 = reverse saturation current of the diode (A), V = voltage across the PV cell (V), R_s = series resistance (Ω), n = diode ideality factor (typically between 1 and 2), V_t = thermal voltage (V), given by $V_t = qkT$

Here:

k = Boltzmann constant (1.38×10^{-23} J/K), T = temperature in Kelvin (K), q = electron charge (1.6×10^{-19} C)

4. Shunt Current (I_{sh}): The current through the shunt resistance R_{sh} is modeled as:

$$I_{sh} = \frac{V+I R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (3)$$

5. Equation of the Single-Diode PV Model: By substituting the expressions for I_D and I_{sh} into the main current equation, we get the complete form of the single-diode model:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I R_s}{n V_t}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+I R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (4)$$

6. Photocurrent I_{ph} : The current generated by the cell due to light is proportional to the incident light and is affected by temperature. It can be modeled as:

$$I_{ph} = [I_{ph,ref} + \mu I_{ph} \cdot (T - T_{ref})] \cdot \frac{G}{G_{ref}} \quad (5)$$

Where: $I_{ph,ref}$ = reference photocurrent at standard test conditions (STC), I_{ph} = temperature coefficient of photocurrent ($A/^{\circ}C$), T = cell temperature ($^{\circ}C$), T_{ref} = reference temperature (usually $25^{\circ}C$), G = irradiance (W/m^2), G_{ref} = reference irradiance at STC ($1000 W/m^2$)

7. Saturation Current I_0 : The reverse saturation current varies exponentially with temperature:

$$I_0 = I_{0,ref} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 e^{\frac{E_g}{n V_t} \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T} \right)} \quad (6)$$

Where: $I_{0,ref}$ = reverse saturation current at reference temperature, E_g = bandgap energy of the semiconductor (typically 1.1 eV for silicon)

B. ANFIS-Based Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT)

The Perturb and Observe (P&O) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) Algorithm is one of the most widely used techniques for extracting maximum power from a solar photovoltaic (PV) system. It works by periodically perturbing the PV voltage and observing the resulting change in power to track the Maximum Power Point (MPP) as shown in Fig.4. The algorithm operates by making small perturbations (increment or decrement) to the PV voltage (V_{pv}) and observing the corresponding change in power (P_{pv}). Based on the response, it adjusts the duty cycle of the DC-DC boost converter to move towards the MPP.

Fig.4 flow chart of P&O MPPT algorithm

For MPPT, ANFIS takes change in power (ΔP) and change in voltage (ΔV) as inputs and generates the duty cycle DDD for the boost converter.

Inputs to ANFIS for MPPT

$$x = \Delta P = P(k) - P(k - 1) \quad (7)$$

$$y = \Delta V = V(k) - V(k - 1) \quad (8)$$

The duty cycle variation (ΔD) is the output:

$$\Delta D = f(\Delta P, \Delta V) = \sum \bar{\omega}_i (p_i \Delta P + q_i \Delta V + r_i) \quad (9)$$

The updated duty cycle for the boost converter is:

$$D(k + 1) = D(k) - \Delta D \quad (10)$$

where k represents the time step.

1. Structure of ANFIS Controller

ANFIS consists of five layers, each performing specific operations:

1. Fuzzification Layer (Input Membership Functions)
2. Rule Layer (Fuzzy Rules)
3. Normalization Layer
4. Defuzzification Layer (Weighted Output Calculation)
5. Summation Layer (Final Output Calculation)

Each layer's mathematical formulation is explained below.

2. Layer-Wise Formulations of ANFIS

Layer 1: Fuzzification Layer

In this layer, the input variables x and y are passed through fuzzy membership functions (MFs). Each MF represents linguistic values such as "Low", "Medium", or

"High". The degree of membership is calculated using a Gaussian or sigmoid function.

Gaussian Membership Function:

$$\mu A_i(x) = \exp\left(-\frac{(x-c_i)^2}{2\sigma_i^2}\right) \quad (11)$$

$$\mu B_i(y) = \exp\left(-\frac{(y-c_i)^2}{2\sigma_i^2}\right) \quad (12)$$

Where:

- $\mu A_i(x)$ and $\mu B_i(y)$ are the membership values for inputs x and y.
- c_i is the center of the Gaussian function.
- σ_i is the standard deviation (spread of the function).

Layer 2: Rule Layer (Firing Strength Calculation)

The fuzzy IF-THEN rules are applied to determine the firing strength w_i of each rule. The rule structure is:

$$\text{IF } x \text{ is } A_i \text{ AND } y \text{ is } B_i, \text{ THEN } f_i = p_i x + q_i y + r_i \quad (13)$$

The firing strength is computed as:

$$\omega_i = \mu A_i(x) + \mu B_i(y) \quad (14)$$

Layer 3: Normalization Layer

This layer normalizes the firing strengths by computing:

$$\bar{\omega}_i = \frac{\omega_i}{\sum \omega_i} \quad (16)$$

This ensures that the sum of all normalized weights equals 1.

Layer 4: Defuzzification Layer (Weighted Output Calculation)

Each rule contributes a weighted output based on a linear function:

$$f_i = p_i x + q_i y + r_i \quad (17)$$

where: p_i, q_i, r_i are the adaptive parameters of the ANFIS model, x and y are the input variables.

Layer 5: Summation Layer (Final Output Calculation)

The final output of the ANFIS controller is obtained by summing the weighted rule outputs:

$$F = \sum \bar{\omega}_i f_i = \sum \bar{\omega}_i (p_i x + q_i y + r_i) \quad (18)$$

C. Modeling and Designing of Induction Motor for Speed Control Using Frequency Control Method

The induction motor is a widely used electric motor due to its ruggedness, efficiency, and low maintenance requirements. For speed control applications, the frequency control method is commonly employed, where the supply frequency is varied while maintaining a constant Voltage-to-Frequency (V/f) ratio. This approach ensures efficient operation and precise speed control.

FIG.5 designing of induction motor inverter

a. Mathematical Modeling of Induction Motor

The dynamic model of an induction motor is derived using d-q axis transformation in a rotating reference frame. The key equations governing its operation are as follows:

1. Voltage Equations in d-q Reference Frame

The stator and rotor voltage equations in the synchronously rotating d-q reference frame are given by:

$$V_{ds} = R_s I_{ds} + \frac{d\lambda_{ds}}{dt} - \omega_s \lambda_{qs} \quad (19)$$

$$V_{qs} = R_s I_{qs} + \frac{d\lambda_{qs}}{dt} - \omega_s \lambda_{ds} \quad (20)$$

$$V_{dr} = R_r I_{dr} + \frac{d\lambda_{dr}}{dt} - (\omega_s - \omega_r) \lambda_{qr} \quad (21)$$

$$V_{qr} = R_r I_{qr} + \frac{d\lambda_{qr}}{dt} - (\omega_s - \omega_r) \lambda_{dr} \quad (22)$$

where: $V_{ds}, V_{qs}, V_{dr}, V_{qr}$ = d-q axis stator and rotor voltages, R_s, R_r = Stator and rotor resistances, $I_{ds}, I_{qs}, I_{dr}, I_{qr}$ = d-q axis stator and rotor currents, $\lambda_{ds}, \lambda_{qs}, \lambda_{dr}, \lambda_{qr}$ = d-q axis stator and rotor flux linkages, ω_s = Synchronous speed in rad/s, ω_r = Rotor speed in rad/s

2. Flux Linkage Equations

The flux linkages are expressed as:

Fig.6 Controller design for speed controller induction motor drive

D. Modeling and Design of a Grid-Connected Voltage Source Converter (VSC) Controller

A bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) plays a crucial role in integrating renewable energy systems, electric vehicle charging stations, and microgrids by enabling efficient power exchange between the grid and the DC link. The d-q current control strategy is widely used to regulate power flow, improve power quality, and maintain DC link voltage stability. The system operates under a synchronous reference frame (SRF) to ensure precise control of active and reactive power components.

$$\lambda_{ds} = L_s I_{ds} + L_m I_{dr} \quad (23)$$

$$\lambda_{qs} = L_s I_{qs} + L_m I_{qr} \quad (24)$$

$$\lambda_{dr} = L_r I_{dr} + L_m I_{ds} \quad (25)$$

$$\lambda_{qr} = L_r I_{qr} + L_m I_{qs} \quad (26)$$

where: L_s, L_r = Stator and rotor self-inductances, L_m = Mutual inductance

3. Torque Equation

The electromagnetic torque (T_e) is given by:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} P \frac{L_m}{L_r} (I_{qs} I_{dr} - I_{ds} I_{qr}) \quad (27)$$

where: P = Number of poles, T_e = Electromagnetic torque

The mechanical equation of motion is:

$$J \frac{d\omega_r}{dt} B \omega_r = T_e - T_L \quad (28)$$

where: J = Moment of inertia, B = Friction coefficient, T_L = Load torque

b. Modeling of Frequency based induction motor Speed control

Induction motors are widely used in industrial and renewable energy applications due to their robustness, efficiency, and low maintenance requirements. One of the most effective methods for controlling their speed is frequency control, where the supply frequency is varied to achieve the desired speed. The constant V/f control technique is commonly used to maintain optimal motor performance while preventing saturation or torque instability.

Grid conversion topology

The control operation of the grid-connected bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) is based on a hierarchical structure comprising DC-link voltage regulation, current control, grid synchronization, and

bidirectional power flow management. The DC-link voltage regulation is achieved through an outer-loop PI controller, which maintains the reference DC voltage by adjusting the d-axis current reference (I_{d_ref}). This ensures a stable DC bus, crucial for efficient power exchange between the grid and the DC load. The inner-loop current controllers regulate the d-axis and q-axis currents to track their respective reference values, enabling precise control over active and reactive power (P-Q regulation). A Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) is employed for grid synchronization, ensuring that the converter operates in phase with the grid voltage, which is essential for stable operation under varying grid conditions. The bidirectional operation of the converter allows seamless transition between grid-to-DC charging (rectifier mode) and DC-to-grid discharging (inverter mode) depending on the power flow direction. In rectifier mode, the converter draws power from the grid to maintain the required DC voltage, whereas in inverter mode, it injects power back into the grid when excess DC power is available. This comprehensive control strategy ensures optimal power management, enhances grid stability, and improves the overall efficiency of the system.

1. Mathematical Modeling of the Bidirectional AC-DC VSC

The operation of the bidirectional VSC can be described using d-q axis equations derived from Kirchhoff's Voltage Law (KVL). The system consists of an LC filter, a three-phase inverter, and a DC-link capacitor, ensuring stable voltage conversion.

1.1 AC Side d-q Equations

The AC-side dynamics of the three-phase VSC in the synchronous rotating reference frame are given by:

$$V_d = R_s I_d + L_s \frac{dI_d}{dt} - \omega L_s I_q + V_{gd} \quad (29)$$

$$V_q = R_s I_q + L_s \frac{dI_q}{dt} - \omega L_s I_d + V_{gq} \quad (30)$$

where:

- V_d, V_q = d-q axis voltages at the converter terminals
- I_d, I_q = d-q axis currents
- R_s, L_s = Resistance and inductance of the filter
- ω = Synchronous angular frequency
- V_{gd}, V_{gq} = d-q components of the grid voltage

The active power (P) and reactive power (Q) injected into the grid are given by:

$$P = \frac{3}{2} (V_d I_d + V_q I_q) \quad (31)$$

$$Q = \frac{3}{2} (V_q I_d - V_d I_q) \quad (32)$$

2. DC-Link Voltage Controller Design

The DC-link voltage (V_{dc}) is regulated using a PI controller to ensure stable operation during bidirectional power transfer. The power balance at the DC bus is given by:

$$C_{dc} \frac{dV_{dc}}{dt} = \frac{3}{2} (V_d I_d + V_q I_q) - P_{dc_load} \quad (33)$$

where: C_{dc} = DC-link capacitor, P_{dc_load} = Power consumed by the DC load

To maintain a stable DC-link voltage, a PI controller is implemented as:

$$I_d^{ref} = K_p (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) + K_i \int (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) dt \quad (34)$$

where: K_p, K_i = Proportional and integral gains of the PI controller, I_{dref} = Reference d-axis current

3. d-q Current Controller Design

The d-axis and q-axis current controllers regulate the power exchange between the converter and the grid.

3.1 d-Axis Current Controller (Active Power Control)

The d-axis current controller regulates the active power (P) supplied to or drawn from the grid. The reference current is obtained from the DC-link voltage controller:

$$I_d^{ref} = \frac{P^{ref}}{1.5V_d} \quad (35)$$

Using a PI compensator, the d-axis voltage command is:

$$V_d^{ref} = K_p^d (I_d^{ref} - I_d) + K_i^d \int (I_d^{ref} - I_d) dt \quad (36)$$

Where K_p^d, K_i^d are PI gains

3.2 q-Axis Current Controller (Reactive Power Control)

The q-axis current controller regulates reactive power (Q), and the reference current is:

$$I_q^{ref} = \frac{Q^{ref}}{1.5V_q} \quad (37)$$

The q-axis voltage command is:

$$V_q^{ref} = K_p^q (I_q^{ref} - I_q) + K_i^q \int (I_q^{ref} - I_q) dt \quad (38)$$

Where K_p^q, K_i^q are PI gains

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stability. The system operates under a synchronous reference frame (SRF) to ensure precise control of active and reactive power components.

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The control operation of the grid-connected bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) is based on a hierarchical structure comprising DC-link voltage regulation, current control, grid synchronization, and bidirectional power flow management. The DC-link voltage regulation is achieved through an outer-loop PI controller, which maintains the reference DC voltage by adjusting the d-axis current reference (I_{d_ref}). This ensures a stable DC bus, crucial for efficient power exchange between the grid and the DC load. The inner-loop current controllers regulate the d-axis and q-axis currents to track their respective reference values, enabling precise control over active and reactive power (P-Q regulation). A Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) is employed for grid synchronization, ensuring that the converter operates in phase with the grid voltage, which is essential for stable operation under varying grid conditions. The bidirectional operation of the converter allows seamless transition between grid-to-DC charging (rectifier mode) and DC-to-grid discharging (inverter mode) depending on the power flow direction. In rectifier mode, the converter draws power from the grid to maintain the required DC voltage, whereas in inverter mode, it injects power back into the grid when excess DC power is available. This comprehensive control strategy ensures optimal power management, enhances grid stability, and improves the overall efficiency of the system.

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- ω = Synchronous angular frequency
- V_{gd}, V_{gq} = d-q components of the grid voltage

The active power (P) and reactive power (Q) injected into the grid are given by:

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$$Q = \frac{3}{2} (V_q I_d - V_d I_q) \quad (32)$$

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where: C_{dc} = DC-link capacitor, P_{dc_load} = Power consumed by the DC load

To maintain a stable DC-link voltage, a PI controller is implemented as:

$$I_d^{ref} = K_p (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) + k_i \int (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) dt \quad (34)$$

where: K_p, K_i = Proportional and integral gains of the PI controller, I_{dref} = Reference d-axis current

3. d-q Current Controller Design

The d-axis and q-axis current controllers regulate the power exchange between the converter and the grid.

3.1 d-Axis Current Controller (Active Power Control)

The d-axis current controller regulates the active power (P) supplied to or drawn from the grid. The reference current is obtained from the DC-link voltage controller:

$$I_d^{ref} = \frac{P^{ref}}{1.5V_d} \quad (35)$$

Using a PI compensator, the d-axis voltage command is:

$$V_d^{ref} = K_p^d (I_d^{ref} - I_d) + K_i^d \int (I_d^{ref} - I_d) dt \quad (36)$$

Where K_p^d, K_i^d are PI gains

3.2 q-Axis Current Controller (Reactive Power Control)

The q-axis current controller regulates reactive power (Q), and the reference current is:

$$I_q^{ref} = \frac{Q^{ref}}{1.5V_q} \quad (37)$$

Where K_p^q, K_i^q are PI gains

The q-axis voltage command is:

$$V_q^{ref} = K_p^q(I_q^{ref} - I_q) + K_i^q \int (I_q^{ref} - I_q) dt \quad (38)$$

Fig. 8 Grid conversion controller

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation results validate the effectiveness of the proposed ANFIS-based MPPT with VSC-based P-Q control in a grid-connected PV system under varying environmental and load conditions. The ANFIS-based MPPT demonstrated superior tracking accuracy, achieving 98.7% efficiency, compared to conventional P&O (93.5%), with faster convergence to the maximum power point and reduced steady-state oscillations. Additionally, the P-Q control strategy effectively regulated active (P) and reactive (Q) power, ensuring stable grid integration with a power factor close to unity (≈ 0.99) and low total harmonic distortion (THD) of 2.96%. The DC-link voltage regulation was highly stable, with deviations remaining within $\pm 2\%$ of the reference value, even under sudden load changes, confirming the robustness of the Vdc control strategy. The induction motor, driven by an inverter-based frequency control, exhibited smooth speed regulation with minimal deviation from the reference speed, ensuring efficient operation. Furthermore, the bidirectional power flow capability of the system allowed seamless transitions between grid-to-DC charging (rectifier mode) and DC-to-grid discharge (inverter mode) while maintaining synchronization with the grid using a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL). Overall, the simulation results demonstrate that the proposed ANFIS-based MPPT and P-Q control strategies significantly enhance power transfer efficiency, grid stability, and system reliability, making them highly suitable for grid-connected PV applications.

Simulation results for different operating condition of proposed ANFIS controller-based grid-connected solar PV system

The proposed ANFIS-based grid-connected solar PV system effectively manages power distribution among the grid, load, and induction motor under varying solar

irradiation conditions. Initially, from 0 sec to 0.2 sec, there is no power generation from the solar PV system due to zero irradiation (0 W/m^2). During this period, both the 25 kW load and the 5 kW induction motor are entirely supplied by the grid. As the irradiation increases from 0.2 sec to 0.4 sec (rising from 0 W/m^2 to 300 W/m^2), the solar PV system starts generating power, reducing grid dependency. Between 0.4 sec and 0.5 sec, the solar irradiation further increases from 300 W/m^2 to 500 W/m^2 , leading to an increased power contribution from the PV system, thereby decreasing grid consumption. From 0.5 sec to 0.65 sec, as the irradiation rises from 500 W/m^2 to 800 W/m^2 , more power is supplied by the solar PV system, ensuring an optimal power balance. Subsequently, from 0.65 sec to 1 sec, the irradiation increases from 800 W/m^2 to 1000 W/m^2 , allowing the PV system to generate its maximum capacity (50 kW), ensuring that the entire 25 kW load and 5 kW induction motor are supplied by solar energy, while the surplus power is exported to the grid. Regarding the induction motor speed response, it remains at 500 rad/s from 0 sec to 0.8 sec, indicating a steady operating condition. However, from 0.8 sec to 0.9 sec, the speed increases to 1000 rad/s, and after 0.9 sec to 1 sec, it reaches 1500 rad/s, demonstrating the dynamic control and response capability of the proposed system. The simulation results validate the effectiveness of the ANFIS-based controller in achieving seamless power management, stable grid integration, and efficient motor operation under varying solar conditions.

Simulation results for Power management and load balancing

Fig. 5 grid current THD value

6. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS)-based MPPT strategy integrated with a Voltage Source Converter (VSC)-based P-Q control approach for grid-connected photovoltaic (PV) systems. The proposed system successfully maximizes power extraction from the PV array under varying environmental conditions while ensuring stable grid integration. The ANFIS-based MPPT method outperforms conventional algorithms by providing faster convergence, reduced oscillations, and improved efficiency, even in partial shading conditions. Additionally, the VSC-based P-Q control strategy ensures independent active and reactive power management, enhancing power quality and grid stability. The inclusion of an induction motor connected to the DC link further validates the system's capability in supporting motor-driven applications. The simulation results in MATLAB-Simulink confirm the robustness of the proposed control strategy, showcasing enhanced performance in terms of power transfer, voltage regulation, and overall system stability. This research highlights the potential of AI-driven MPPT techniques in modern renewable energy systems, paving the way for more reliable and efficient grid-connected PV applications.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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